

Estimation of wood density by core drilling technique

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Abstract: Density estimation by non-destructive or semi-destructive methods are applied mainly on softwood species. The instruments are expensive, the methods are complicated, and the determination coefficients are low. In the present study, the simple core hollow drilling approach is revisited. Data of 600 cores or cylindrical specimens from 300 pieces of 10 different softwood and hardwood species have been evaluated in the density range from 350 to 975 kg m⁻³. The data were obtained from complete pieces and from the cores from core drilling, while a difference between the two data sets is 1.7%. At higher densities, the differences are greater. A model was proposed concerning the piece density estimation with a determination coefficient of 0.98. It is concluded that core drill is a cheap and reliable method for density estimation and the data are equally reliable for radial or tangential probing. The cylindrical cores obtained are suitable to moisture content and species determination.

Keywords: Core drill, Density, Non-destructive testing, Sawn timber, Semi-destructive test, Wood.

Introduction

Non-destructive or semi-destructive techniques (NDT or SDT) gained popularity for timber grading also in built-in wood constructions, which are always in connection with density estimation (Casado et al. 2012; Shalbafan et al. 2013; Ponneth et al. 2014; Íñiguez-González et al. 2015a; Soriano et al. 2015; Silva-Oliveira et al. 2017; Llana et al. 2018a; Martínez et al. 2018), as density is well-correlated with mechanical properties. From density combined with other NDTs, the dynamic modulus of elasticity (MOE_{dyn}) can be calculated (Meierhofer 1988; Ross et al. 1994 and 1998; Divós and Tanaka 1997; Arriaga et al. 2002; Pellerin and Ross 2002; Ishiguri et al. 2008; Esteban et al. 2009; Tannert et al. 2014; Ross 2015). Resistance measurements for needle and drill penetration and screw pullout are the most widely applied NDTs for built-in wood structures, which rely on the energy determination needed to insert needles or drills into or pull out a screw from timber. However, the determination coefficients (R²) of the obtained data to real densities are in the range of 0.30 to 0.60 (Bobadilla et al. 2007 and 2009; Montón 2012; Kloiber et al. 2014; Íñiguez-González et al. 2015b). A high value resistograph instrument gave R² values of 0.50 to 0.90 (Rinn et al. 1996; Mariño et al. 2002; Acuña et al. 2011; Kloiber et al. 2014). A device based on measuring the pin penetration force resulted in R² values in the range of 0.70 to 0.78 (Kloiber et al. 2012).

The core drilling techniques (CDTs) work with a hollow drill or increment borer and are versatile and deliver not only data of density and physical and mechanical properties. The increment borer was described already in the 19th century (Pressler 1866), which gives good results on standing trees (Smith 1955; Walters and Bruckmann 1964; Bergsten et al. 2001; Wiemann and Williamson 2013). Interestingly, CDT is suitable for testing of gypsum, mortar, and concrete (Kasal et al. 2003). Kloiber et al. (2006) found R² from 0.30 to 0.60 for density estimation by CDT of silver fir and Norway spruce. Kasal (2003) achieved R² in the range from 0.67 to 0.89 in 5 species (white ash, sugar maple, red cedar, southern yellow pine and red oak), Íñiguez-González et al. (2015b) found R² in the range of 0.80 to 0.89 for radiata

pine, and Llana et al. (2018b) reported R^2 from 0.84 to 0.89 for Norway spruce from built-in structures.

CDT has the advantage that it is also suitable to estimate moisture content (MC), species determination, and analysis of the kind of a biological degradation. In case of long drills, dendrochronology analysis can also be performed. A disadvantage of CDT is the hole left behind, which may have 20 mm diameter. According to Falk et al. (2003), such a hole does not have a significant effect on mechanical properties. If several measurements have to be performed to obtain good results (Kasal 2003; Kasal et al. 2003; Kasal and Anthony 2004; Bobadilla et al. 2007 and 2009; Tannert et al. 2014), too many holes may be an aesthetical problem that can be solved using wooden dowels if necessary.

The accurate estimation of wood density of structural members in restoration and rehabilitation works is still a pending issue. CDT is simple and economical with its advantages described above. However, the available data material concerning CDT is limited, mainly because it is more frequently applied to softwoods. The goal of the present paper was to collect CDT data also from hardwoods and to increase the specimen number to improve the statistical reliability of the obtained physical and mechanical data.

Material and methods

A total of 300 specimens from 10 softwood and hardwood species were measured (Table 1). Thirty 95 x 65 mm² cross-section and 200 mm long specimens were tested for each wood species. Most of these wood species are part of built-in timber structures in Spain (poplar, maritime pine, Scots pine, Salzmänn pine, sweet chestnut and European oak). The selected species represent a wide range of densities (350 to 975 kg m⁻³). The specimens were conditioned at 20 ±2°C and 65 ±5% relative humidity (RH). Specimen dimensions were measured with a resolution of 0.01 mm and mass with ±0.01 g. Density was calculated: $\rho = m/v$ (Eq. 1), where ρ is the density in kg m⁻³, m the mass in kg and v the volume in m³.

Two cores were extracted from each specimen, one in radial direction and the other in tangential direction (Fig. 1A). Fig. 1B shows a 140 mm long CMT brand hollow drill bit, 20 mm in outer diameter and 10 mm inner diameter. The drilling depth was 60 mm. The cores were removed by a screwdriver to break the end of the core (Fig. 1C). The presented drill bits were selected for stability and reliability for on-site application. Other types of drills with a more favorable inner/outer diameter ratio have been tested previously (Montón 2012; Iñiguez-González et al. 2015b; Llana et al. 2018b), where auxiliary elements had to be used to guarantee the stability and safety of the process. The internal end of cores was irregular because of the screwdriver extraction, so that the cores were cut to a standard length of 50 mm. The density of the cores was determined as usual (Eq. 1).

Results and discussion

Mean density values (ρ) and coefficients of variation (COV) are listed in Table 2, which show higher COV for pine species (around 9%) than for the other ones (around 3%). This may be due to the great differences between sapwood and heartwood, high knottiness, and/or the high resin content typical of pines. Significant differences between 8 species were found at a confidence level of 95%. No significant differences are seen between maritime pine and Scots pine, or between Salzmänn pine, sweet chestnut, and iroko partly because these species have similar densities (Table 3 and Fig. 2A).

There are no significant differences between radial (R) and tangential (T) core densities at a confidence level of 95% (Fig. 2B). Iñiguez-González et al. (2015b) reported on similar findings in case of coniferous species. Needle penetration resistance and screw pullout resistance measurements also gave similar data (Bobadilla et al. 2007; Martínez 2016). It can be concluded that the anatomical differences (R or T) in CDT are not significant.

Table 2 and Figure 2C show slightly higher core densities than specimen densities with the exception of western red cedar and radiata pine. The average difference between the two data sets is 1.7% and no significant differences between both densities were found. Similar results were reported by Kloiber and Kotlinová (2006) for silver fir and Norway spruce. According to Montón (2012) and Íñiguez-González et al. (2015b), who studied CDT of radiata pine with drilling bits with different core diameters, the differences between core density and specimen density are greater in case of smaller cylindrical cores. The differences were explained by different fiber crushing ratios obtained with different drill types.

The statistical data evaluation reveals: the higher is the species' density, the greater is the ratio 'core density/specimen density'. However, around a density $\approx 700 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, this ratio becomes stable (Figure 3). In fact, significant differences between core density and specimen density were found for the species with the highest density (European oak and missanda). This effect seems to be consistent, given that friction and fiber crushing depend on density. However, the opposite effect was found by application of the method 'drilling chip extraction', where chip density was lower than specimen density because of the MC loss due to the drilling heat (Bobadilla et al. 2013; Martínez 2016). But this effect is lower in the case of CDT, partly, because the solid cylinders do not lose so much moisture than the porous chips, and partly because of the absence of air ventilation. Moreover, high quality drills cause less friction and heat development. The higher densities of cores in relation to the specimen densities (Table 2 and Figure 2C) are indicative for less moisture evaporation due to friction heat. Nevertheless, humidity loss should be the subject of future research.

In Fig. 4 is a lineal regression model presented describing the correlation between specimen density and cylindrical core mass. Here, because of the same core volumes, dimensional measurements are not necessary. The consideration of R and T sampling is not necessary, either. The model equation is:

$$\rho = 228 m_c + 45, \text{ (Eq. 2), } R^2 0.98, \text{ StE } 22.27 \text{ kg m}^{-3},$$

where "ρ" is specimen density in kg m^{-3} and "m_c" is the core mass in g. StE is the standard error. The relation is significant at the confidence level of 95%.

The presented model estimates density more accurately than other NDTs cited in the introduction.

It is promising that the CDT described here could be applied for several softwoods and hardwoods in a wide density range of 350 to 975 kg m^{-3} . On the other hand, the MC of $12 \pm 2\%$ of the investigated material lowers the reliability of the method applied for materials with higher MC. Another problem is the high resin level of some species with densities higher than 600 kg m^{-3} . Because of the development of irritating dust from western red cedar and iroko, the worker should wear individual protection equipment. The drill should be cooled after every core drilling and this measurement is more necessary for high density wood species. Dust from European oak increases drill friction and drilling heat development. If applied for built-in wood structures, the drill hole should be closed by wooden dowels to avoid the penetration of fungi and also for aesthetic reasons.

Conclusions

Core drilling is a useful method for density estimation. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.98 in the density range of 350 to 975 kg m^{-3} at $12 \pm 2\%$ MC. Other NDT techniques result in lower R^2 values. To measure core dimensions is not necessary because the method relies on mass measurement. The results do not differ between R and T measurement. Core density is 1.7% higher than the density measured by traditional methods on complete pieces. The higher the species density, the greater is this difference. In case of the highest density species, European oak and missanda, this difference was statistically relevant. The relationship between the density of the species and core/specimen density ratio has a logarithmic tendency that stabilizes in densities around 700 kg m^{-3} or above. In summary, the

core drilling method is accurate, reliable, easy and cheap. The method is semi-destructive, but the holes do not have a significant effect on the mechanical properties. An advantage is that the cores permit the MC and species determination.

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References

- Acuña, L., Basterra, L.A., Casado, M.M., López, G., Ramón-Cueto, G., Relea, E., Martínez, C., González, A. (2011). Aplicación del resistógrafo a la obtención de la densidad y la diferenciación de especies de madera [Application of resistograph to obtain the density and to differentiate wood species]. *Mater. Construcc.* 61(303):451-464.
- Arriaga, F., Peraza, F., Esteban, M., Bobadilla, I., García, F. (2002). Intervención en estructuras de madera. [Assessment of timber structures] Ed. Aitim. Madrid. 476 pp.
- Bergsten, U., Lindeberg, J., Rindby, A., Evans, R. (2001). Batch measurements of wood density on intact or prepared drill cores using x-ray microdensitometry. *Wood Sci. Technol.* 35:435-452
- Bobadilla, I., Íñiguez-González, G., Esteban, M., Arriaga, F., Casas, L. (2007). Density estimation by screw withdrawal resistance and probing in structural sawn coniferous timber. Proceedings of the 15th International Symposium on Nondestructive Testing of Wood. Pp. 247-251. September 10-12. Duluth, MN, USA.
- Bobadilla, I., Íñiguez-González, G., Arriaga, F., Esteban, M. (2009). Técnicas no destructivas en la inspección de estructuras de madera I: El penetrómetro [NDT on timber structures assessment: Penetration tester]. *BIT AiTiM.* 260:66-70.
- Bobadilla, I., Martínez, R.D., Calvo, J., Arriaga, F., Íñiguez-González, G. (2013). First steps in wood density estimation using a conventional drill. 18th International Nondestructive Testing and Evaluation of Wood Symposium. Pp. 112-118. September 24-27. Madison, WI, USA.
- Casado, M.M., Acuña, L., Basterra, L.A., Ramón-Cueto, G., Vecilla, D. (2012). Grading of structural timber of *Populus x euroamericana* clone I-214. *Holzforschung*, 66(5):633-638.
- Divós, F., Tanaka, T. (1997). Lumber strength estimation by multiple regression. *Holzforschung*, 51(5):467-471.
- Esteban, M., Bobadilla, I., Arriaga, F., Íñiguez-González, G., García, H. (2009). NDT applied to estimate the mechanical properties of the timber of an ancient structure in Valsaín, Segovia (Spain). Proceedings of 16th International Symposium on Nondestructive Testing of Wood. Pp. 152-157. October 12-14. Beijing, China.
- Falk, R.H., DeVisser, D., Plume, G.R., Fridley, K.J. (2003). Effect of drilled holes on the bending strength of large dimension Douglas-fir lumber. *Forest Prod. J.* 53(5):55-60.
- Íñiguez-González, G., Arriaga, F., Esteban, M., Llana, D.F. (2015a). Reference conditions and modification factors for the standardization of nondestructive variables used in the evaluation of existing timber structures. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 101:1166-1171.
- Íñiguez-González, G., Montón, J., Arriaga, F., Segués, E. (2015b). In-situ assessment of structural timber density using non-destructive and semi-destructive testing. *BioResources.* 10(2):2256-2265.
- Ishiguri, F., Matsui, R., Iizuka, K., Yokota, S., Yoshizawa, N. (2008). Prediction of the mechanical properties of lumber by stress-wave velocity and Pilodyn penetration of 36-year-old Japanese larch trees. *Holz Roh Werkst.*, 66:275-280.

- Kasal, B. (2003). Semi-Destructive Method for In-situ Evaluation of Compressive Strength of Wood Structural Members. *Forest Prod. J.* 53(11/12):55-58.
- Kasal, B., Drdäcký, M., Jirovsky, I. (2003). Semidestructive methods for evaluation of timber structures. *Structural Studies, Repairs and Maintenance of Heritage Architecture VIII*. C.A. Brebia, Editor. *Advances in Architecture*. WIT Press. Southampton, pp. 835-842
- Kasal, B., Anthony, R. (2004) *Advances in in situ evaluation of timber structures*. *Prog. Struct. Eng. Mat.* 6:94-103.
- Kloiber, M., Kotlínová, M. (2006). Prediction of mechanical properties by means of radial cores in situ,” NSF/MŠMT supported US-Czech project and RILEM Workshop. *In-Situ Evaluation of Historic Wood and Masonry Structures*. Prague, Czech Republic.
- Kloiber, M., Tippner, J., Praus, L., Hrivnák, J. (2012). Experimental verification of a new tool for wood mechanical resistance measurement. *Wood Res-Slovakia* 57(3):383-398.
- Kloiber, M., Tippner, J., Hrivnák, J. (2014). Mechanical properties of wood examined by semi-destructive devices. *Mater. Struct.* 47(1-2):199-212.
- Llana, D.F., Hermoso, E., Bobadilla, I., Íñiguez-González, G. (2018a). Influence of moisture content on the results of penetration and withdrawal resistance measurements on softwoods. *Holzforschung*, 22.01.2018, published online
- Llana, D.F., Íñiguez-González, G., Montón, J., Arriaga, F. (2018b). In-situ density estimation by four nondestructive techniques on Norway spruce from built-in wood structures. *Holzforschung*, 05.06.2018, published online
- Mariño, R., Fernández, M.E., Fernández, C. (2002). Análisis comparativo de la densidad de la madera de *Pinus sylvestris* L. mediante la utilización del resistógrafo [Comparative analysis of wood density from *Pinus sylvestris* L. using resistograph]. *Revista CIS-Madera* 9:60-70.
- Martínez, R.D. (2016). Métodos no destructivos de estimación de la densidad de madera. [Timber density estimation by non-destructive methods]. Doctoral thesis. Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, EPS de Lugo. 214 p. PDF file: <https://minerva.usc.es/xmlui/handle/10347/15159>
- Martínez, R.D., Calvo, J., Arriaga, F., Bobadilla, I. (2018). In situ density estimation of timber pieces by drilling residue analysis. *Eur. J. Wood Prod.* 76:509-515.
- Meierhofer, U. (1988). Schraubenauszugfestigkeit und Tragfähigkeit von Fichten- und Tannenholz. [Screw withdrawal resistance and strength of spruce and fir]. *Holz Roh Werkst.* 46:15-17.
- Montón, J. (2012). Clasificación estructural de la Madera de *Pinus radiata* D. Don procedente de Cataluña mediante métodos no destructivos y su aplicabilidad en la diagnosis estructural [Structural timber grading of *Pinus radiata* D. Don from Catalonia using NDT and applicability in structural assessment]. Doctoral thesis. Universidad Politécnica de Cataluña, Departamento de construcciones arquitectónicas I. 2 vol. 486 p. PDF: <http://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/96423>
- Pellerin, R.F., Ross, R.J. (2002). *Nondestructive evaluation of wood*. Forest products society. Madison, WI. 53705-2295. 210 pp.
- Ponnet, D., Vasu, A.E., Easwaran, J.C., Mohandass, A., Chauhan, S.S. (2014). Destructive and non-destructive evaluation of seven hardwoods and analysis of data correlation. *Holzforschung* 68(8):951-956.
- Pressler, M.R. (1866). Der forstliche Zuwachsbohrer [The forestry increment borer]. In: *Tharander Jahrbuch*. Arnoldische Buchhandlung, Leipzig. Dritte Abtheilung III, pp. 137-209.
- Rinn, F., Schweingruber, F.H., Schär, E. (1996) Resistograph and X-ray density charts of wood. Comparative evaluation of drill resistance profiles and X-ray density charts for different wood species. *Holzforschung*, 50(8):303–311.

- Ross, R.J., Pellerin, R.F. (1994). Non-destructive testing for assessing wood members in structures: A review. USDA Forest Service, Forest Products Laboratory, FPL-GTR-70, Madison, WI. 40 pp.
- Ross, R.J., Soltis, L.A., Otton, P. (1998). Assessing wood members in the USS Constitution using non-destructive evaluation methods. *APT Bulletin, The Journal of Preservation Technology*. 29(2):21-25.
- Ross, R.J. (Ed). (2015). *Nondestructive evaluation of wood: Second Edition*. General Technical Report FPL-GTR-238. Madison, WI: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Products Laboratory. 169 pp.
- Shalbfan, A., Luedtke, J., Welling, J., Fruehwald, A. (2013). Physiomechanical properties of ultra-lightweight foam core particleboard: different core densities. *Holzforschung* 67(2):169-175.
- Silva-Oliveira, J.T., Wang, X., Vidaurre, G.B. (2017). Assessing specific gravity of young Eucalyptus plantation trees using a resistance drilling technique. *Holzforschung* 71(2):137-145.
- Smith, D.M. (1955). A comparison of two methods for determining the specific gravity of small samples of second-growth Douglas-fir. Report 2033. Forest Products Laboratory, Madison, WI, USA. 21 pp.
- Soriano, J., Veiga, N.S., Martins, I.Z. (2015). Wood density estimation using the sclerometric method. *Eur. J. Wood Prod*, 73:756-758.
- Tannert, T., Anthony, R.W., Kasal, B., Kloiber, M., Piazza, M., Riggio, M., Rinn, F., Widmann, R., Yamaguchi, N. (2014). In situ assessment of structural timber using semi-destructive techniques. *Mater. Struct.* 47(5):767-785.
- Walters, C.S., Bruckmann, G. (1964). A comparison of methods for determining volume of increment cores. *J. Forest*, 62(3):172-177.
- Wiemann, M.C., Williamson, G.B. (2013). Biomass determination using wood specific gravity from increment cores. General Technical Report 225. Forest Products Laboratory, Madison, WI, USA. 7 pp.

Table 1. The common and botanical names of wood species investigated

#	Common name	Botanical name
1	Western red cedar	<i>Thuja plicata</i> Donn. ex D. Don
2	Black poplar	<i>Populus x euroamericana</i> (Dade) Guinier
3	Radiata pine	<i>Pinus radiata</i> D. Don
4	Maritime pine	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Ait. ssp. <i>mesogeensis</i> Fieschi & Gaussen
5	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> L.
6	Salzmann pine	<i>Pinus nigra</i> Arnold. ssp. <i>salzmannii</i> (Dunal) Franco
7	Sweet chestnut	<i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
8	European oak	<i>Quercus robur</i> L.
9	Iroko	<i>Milicia excelsa</i> (Welw.) C.C.Berg.
10	Missanda	<i>Erythrophleum</i> Afzel ex G. Don Sp.

Table 2. Average densities of specimens and cores

#	Species	Specimen density (ρ)		Density (ρ) of cores					
				ρ radial		ρ tangential		ρ mean	
		Mean (kg m ⁻³)	COV (%)	Mean (kg m ⁻³)	COV (%)	Mean (kg m ⁻³)	COV (%)	Mean (kg m ⁻³)	COV (%)
1	Western red cedar	347	1.7	347	3.1	347	3.8	347	2.7
2	Black poplar	504	2.4	509	3.0	514	4.0	513	2.7
3	Radiata pine	476	8.9	471	9.3	471	11.0	471	9.6
4	Maritime pine	543	9.6	553	11.3	553	11.8	554	11.2
5	Scots pine	573	6.3	581	8.4	572	10.4	576	8.8
6	Salzmann pine	585	12.1	607	12.5	604	13.6	605	13.0
7	Sweet chestnut	615	7.7	618	8.3	629	8.6	622	8.2
8	European oak	672	3.4	690	4.6	705	4.5	697	4.1
9	Iroko	617	5.0	635	6.1	629	7.2	632	6.4
10	Missanda	975	1.2	1000	2.0	998	1.9	999	1.7
Average of all		591	27.0	601	28.1	603	28.3	601	28.3

Table 3. Statistically significant differences between species

#	Species	Mean core ρ (kg m ⁻³)	Homo-geneous groups
1	Western red cedar	347	X
3	Radiata pine	471	X
2	Black poplar	513	X
4	Maritime pine	554	X
5	Scots pine	573	X
6	Salzmann pine	605	X
7	Sweet chestnut	622	X X
9	Iroko	632	X
8	European oak	697	X
10	Missanda	999	X

Figure 1. Drilling procedure. (A) Cylindrical cores extracted in radial and tangential direction, (B) CMT brand 20/10 mm model hollow drill bit, (C) drilling process: a) after using a hollow drill bit, b) core extraction using a screwdriver, c) core and hole

Figure 2. Density diagrams. (A) Box and whisker plot of core densities, (B) Cylindrical core density in radial (R) and tangential (T) directions, (C) Overall difference between core and wood specimen densities.

Figure 3. Logarithmic regression between wood species density and the difference between core and specimen density (up), and core-specimen density ratio (down).

Figure 4. Linear regression between specimen density and cylindrical core mass.